

Tactile trigeminal region acuity in temporomandibular disorders: A reliability and cross-sectional study.

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ABSTRACT

Background: Two-point discrimination (2-PD) is a valuable test for measuring tactile acuity that provides relevant information about cortical reorganisation and somatosensory function.

Objectives: The main objectives of the present study were to assess intra- and inter- examiner reliability of the 2-PD test in the trigeminal region in asymptomatic individuals and only intra-examiner reliability in patients with temporomandibular disorders(TMD). The secondary objective was to observe the correlations of the 2-PD testwith regard to pain intensity and psychological and disability variables.

Methods: Intra- and interexaminer reliability of 2-PD in the trigeminal region was assessed in 40 asymptomatic individuals and 54 patients with TMD. Each clinician received training in the assessment of 2-PD using an esthesiometer and following a standardised protocol for the three branches of trigeminal nerve.

Results: In the asymptomatic participants, interexaminer (intra-class correlation co-efficient (ICC .64-.88) and test-retest (ICC .70-.87) values were obtained. Given simi-lar test-retest values were shown in the group of patients with TMD (ICC .72-.86), the reliability were considered good-moderate. Statistically significant differences($P < .001$) were obtained between the asymptomatic participants and the patients with TMD regarding the mean values from trials of the three trigeminal branch measurements, with a large effect size.

Conclusion: Reliability of the 2-PD test was considered good-moderate. Patients with TMD showed greater distances in the 2-PD test, suggesting

that tactile acuity in the trigeminal region is impaired in patients with TMD. Assessment of tactile acuity with 2-PD test in patients with TMD should be considered clinically.

KEY WORDS

reliability, somatosensory function, tactile acuity, temporomandibular disorders, trigeminal nerve, two-point discrimination

INTRODUCTION

Temporomandibular disorders (TMDs) comprise a wide variety of disorders that affect the anatomy or function of the temporomandibular joint and its associated structures.¹ TMDs are the main cause of nonodontogenic orofacial pain, with considerable prevalence and chronicity rates.² They also involve high costs in terms of both greater disability and socioeconomic level and are frequently associated with psychological disorders such as pain catastrophism.³⁻⁵

The onset and persistence of pain in patients with TMD can be related to an impairment in the manner in which the central nervous system (CNS) receives and processes nociceptive stimuli.⁶ Previous research has suggested that these patients show generalised hyperalgesia, structural and functional changes at the cortical level, and increased areas of pain, all of which are compatible with a central sensitisation process.⁷ In addition, these types of CNS alterations can lead to a disorder in the processing of somatosensory stimuli, as well as an impairment in tactile acuity.⁸

Previous research has shown an alteration in tactile acuity in patients with chronic neck pain.⁸ Furthermore, an association has been found between these alterations and changes at the level of the somatosensory cortex (S1) in patients with complex regional pain syndrome⁹ or chronic low back pain.¹⁰ Considering that tactile acuity depends strictly on the correct functioning of the somatosensory system, it has been suggested that the evaluation of tactile sensitivity and acuity using tests such as two-point discrimination (2-PD) could be a useful indicator of cortical structural alterations in the S1 region

as well as of somatosensory function.

The 2-PD test was designed to evaluate tactile acuity, showing the smallest distance between two mechanical pressure points that can be perceived by the individual as two distinct points.¹¹ The 2-PD test has been proven to be reliable and has been validated in areas such as the cervical and lumbar spine, hand and foot, as well as in patients with chronic neck or lumbar pain.¹²⁻¹⁴

Neurosensory tests aim to evaluate somatosensory alterations.¹⁵ One of the most relevant aspects to evaluate is tactile perception, by means of sensory tests that evaluate the fibres type A myelinated fibres.¹⁶ Of all the tests used to assess tactile sensation, 2-PD has been widely used to assess the condition of mechanoreceptors.¹⁵ It is widely documented that tactile acuity varies according to the body area assessed.¹⁷ The sensory neural pathways in charge of the orofacial zone such as the lip and tongue, or those of the fingers are particularly specialised in the processing of spatial information; therefore, damage to these pathways is likely to manifest more prominently as a loss of spatial acuity. For this reason, accurate measurement of spatial resolution in these regions is particularly important.¹⁷

However, although the 2-PD test appears to be valuable for measuring tactile acuity and provides relevant information about somatosensory cortical reorganisation, some authors have noted the current lack of reliable validation studies for 2-PD test measurement protocols in various body regions and in other pathological pain conditions.¹⁸

Although there are no reliable data for the 2-PD in patients with TMD, there are data in healthy population.¹⁹ The main objectives of the present study were

to assess intra- and interexaminer reliability of the 2-PD test in the trigeminal region in asymptomatic individuals and only intra-examiner reliability in patients with TMD. The secondary objective was to observe the correlations of the 2-PD test with regard to pain intensity and psychological and disability variables

METHODS

Study design

The present research was a reliability and cross-sectional study with a non-probabilistic sample. The interexaminer and test-retest intra-examiner concordance was analysed to assess reliability. The study was planned and conducted in accordance with the Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology statement²⁰ and the Guidelines for Reporting Reliability and Agreement Studies.²¹

Participants

A convenience sample of asymptomatic individuals was obtained from our university campus and the local community using flyers, posters and social media. The inclusion criteria were age between 18 and 65 years; and as exclusion criteria, having chronic or acute pain, neurological disease, or any other inflammatory or degenerative systemic disease, or a history of craniofacial trauma. This was assessed through a questionnaire.

The other convenience sample of symptomatic individuals consisted of

patients with TMD recruited from two private clinics specialising in craniofacial pain and TMD in Madrid, Spain. A diagnosis of chronic TMD of muscular origin (pain persisting for at least 6 months) was necessary for inclusion. According to Diagnostic Criteria for Temporomandibular Disorders (DCTMDs), patients diagnosed with bilateral myofascial pain-related TMD with or without referral were included (pain in a masticatory structure modified by jaw movement, function or parafunction; and familiar pain after palpation in the temporalis and masseter muscle)²² with no other coexisting TMD diagnosis. Patients were excluded if they had a diagnosis of fibromyalgia or rheumatologic disease, any type of cancer, previous spinal or craniomandibular surgery, diagnosis of psychiatric disorder, myelopathy or a history of whiplash trauma. Participants were also excluded from both groups if they were taking medication such as opioids, anticonvulsants, antidepressants or regularly high dosed non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), while NSAIDs as needed were allowed.

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and was approved by the local ethics committee (CSEULS- PI-171/2017). Prior to their participation, the participants provided written informed consent.

Evaluators

Each of the three physical therapists who were in charge of the measurements received a specific 120-minute training session on how to

use the esthesiometer and followed a standardised protocol for the three branches of the trigeminal nerve. Training was performed with eight individuals whose measurements were not included in the study. The physical therapists were recently graduated and had between 0 and 1 year of experience in patients with TMD.

Instrumentation

The Baseline[®] two-point discriminator (esthesiometer; reference: 12-1480, dimensions: 30.48 × 5.08 × 5.08 cm and weight: 0.611 kg) was used to measure tactile acuity in the 2-PD test. This monofilament is equipped with easily sliding scales calibrated as close as possible to 0.1 and with special vinyl tips that minimise the influence of temperature or touch. It is a small plastic device with two small round points and a ruler in millimetres marking the distance between the two points. The application of the two points to the skin generates the tactile stimulus. The application of the device must be perpendicular to the skin, applying both points at the same time, with a pressure that generates a slight depression to the skin, for 1 second. There was an interval of 5 seconds between each stimulus. The esthesiometer is a validated device that shows good reliability (intra- class correlation coefficient [ICC] .76-.93).²³

Procedures

The assessments were performed between December 2017 and June 2018 in our university laboratory. Each healthy participant visited the laboratory on

two different occasions separated by 48 hours. Each patient with TMD visited the laboratory on three different occasions separated by 48 hours (between trials 1 and 2) and 9 days (between trials 2 and 3) (Figure 1). In addition, the participants who took any type of medication and/or received physical therapy, as well as those who met any exclusion criteria during the time period between trials were considered lost to follow-up. The raters used a collection sheet to record the measurements. Before the assessments, the participants removed their eyeglasses, hats, and all jewellery, and lay supine with closed eyes during the procedure. The three branches of the trigeminal nerve were assessed randomly: (V₁) forehead (1 cm lateral to the brow and 2 cm cranial); (V₂) cheek (2 cm lateral from the nasal line and 2 cm caudal to the eye corner); and (V₃) jaw (middle point of the mandibular body 2 cm cranial from the inferior border) (Figure 2). The assessment was performed on both sides, and a mean was calculated.

A starting distance in the esthesiometer, enough for the participant to correctly discriminate, was established for each of the measured points: V₁, 20 mm; V₂, 20 mm; and V₃, 10 mm.¹⁵ Alternating stimuli with increasing and decreasing distance were applied during each series to avoid the expectation of a continuous decreasing. The distance was reduced initially by 5 mm, and subsequently only changes of 1 mm were made to achieve three correct responses of discrimination at the smallest distance. The position of both esthesiometer points was modified for each stimulus. The participants were asked to give one of the following replies after the application of the stimulus: '1', if they felt only one stimulus; '2', if they felt two stimuli; and 'I don't know' if they were not able to discriminate

1 or 2; this response was considered as incorrect, together with '1'. Among the asymptomatic participants, the procedure was performed by raters 1 and 2 on day 1 (trial 1), the order of the raters being randomised, with a duration of 15 minutes each and a pause of 30 minutes between the assessments. After the complete physical assessment of the 2-PD tests on day 1, the participants completed the self-reported measures only at this time. The second assessments (trial 2) were performed 48 hours later, starting in the inverse order of raters from day 1. The same protocol was followed. The assessment was performed by only one rater for the patients with TMD, and a third assessment was performed on day 9 (trial 3).

Self-reported measures

Craniofacial pain and disability

The Craniofacial Pain and Disability Inventory (CF-PDI) is a self-administered questionnaire designed to measure pain, disability and functional status of the mandibular and craniofacial regions. It consists of 21 items leading to a score ranging from 0 to 63 points. The CF-PDI has good structure, internal consistency, reproducibility and construct validity.²⁴

Pain catastrophising

The level of catastrophising related to pain was explored using the Spanish version of the pain catastrophising scale (PCS), which is a reliable and valid measure of pain catastrophising. The PCS consists of 13 items structured by

three factors: rumination, magnification and helplessness. The items are answered with a numeric value between 0 (not at all) and 4 (all the time), resulting in a maximum score of 52 points, with higher scores indicating greater pain catastrophising.²⁵

Pain Intensity

A visual analogue scale (VAS) was used to measure pain intensity before and after each measurement. The VAS comprises a 100 mm horizontal line from 0 mm representing 'no pain' to 100 mm representing 'pain as bad as you can imagine'. The patient placed a mark on the line at the point that they felt represented their intensity at the time, which was quantified by the assessor in mm. This scale has proven its reliability and validity for the measurement of pain intensity.²⁶

Sample size

The sample size was calculated using the method described by Walter et al,²⁷ which is recommended for estimating sample sizes based on the ICC. A minimal acceptable ICC value of $P_0 = .75$ and an expected value of $P_1 = .59$ were chosen. To obtain a power of 80% ($\beta = .2$) and a significance level of 5%, we determined that a sample of at least 40 healthy participants was required for intra-rater reliability (two sets of two measurements were performed each day for 2 days). The calculation of the sample size for patients with TMDs was based on the test-retest (one set of measurements was performed each day for 3 days). For this calculation, a minimally

acceptable ICC value of $P_0 = .75$ and an expected value of $P_1 = .60$ were chosen. To obtain a power of 80% ($\beta = .2$) and a significance level of 5%, we determined that a sample of at least 40 patients was required. To estimate the sample size, we used Power Analysis and Sample Size software (PASS 12).

Data analysis

The data were analysed using the SPSS statistical package (SPSS v.20.0; IBM Corporation). We used the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test to analyse the normal distribution ($P > .05$) of the variables, and a value of $P < .05$ was considered statistically significant.

Reliability was evaluated using the ICC. ICCs with a 95% CI were used to assess inter- and intra-rater reliability and intra-rater test-retest of the 2-PD test score using a 2-way mixed effects analysis of variance, with type consistency of single measurements. ICC values were interpreted according to guidelines established by Shrout and Fleiss,²⁸ in which values $>.75$ indicate excellent reliability, $.6-.75$ good reliability, $.4-.59$ fair reliability and $<.4$ poor reliability.

We expressed the measurement error as a standard error of measurement (SEM), which was calculated as: $SD \times \sqrt{1 - ICC}$, in which SD is the SD of the values from all of the participants and ICC is the reliability coefficient.²⁹ The measurement error is the systematic and random error of a patient's score that is not attributable to the true changes in the construct being measured.³⁰

Responsiveness was assessed using the minimal detectable change

(MDC). MDC_{90} expresses the minimal change required to be 90% confident that the observed change between the two measurements reflects real change and not measurement error³¹; it is calculated as $SEM \times 2 \times 1.96$.

We used an independent *t* test to analyse 2-PD test data, using the mean of trials 1 and 2 by comparing the collection data for the two samples. The effect sizes (Cohen's *d*) were calculated for the outcome variables. According to Cohen's method, the magnitude of the effect was classified as small (0.20-0.49), medium (0.50-0.79) or large (≥ 0.8).³²

Pearson's correlation coefficient was used to analyse the association between the variables of pain-related disability and psychology and the 2-PD test on the trigeminal region data in patients with TMD. A Pearson's correlation coefficient $>.60$ indicated a strong correlation, a coefficient between $.30$ and $.60$ indicated a moderate correlation, and a coefficient below $.30$ indicated a low or very low correlation.³³

Finally, A multiple linear regression analysis was performed to estimate the strength of the associations in the 2-PD test in patients with TMD. Craniofacial pain and disability pain catastrophising and pain intensity were used as predictors. Variance inflation factors (VIFs) were calculated to determine whether there were any multi-collinearity issues in any models. The strength of the association was examined using regression coefficients (β), *P* values and adjusted R^2 . Standardised beta coefficients were reported for each predictor variable included in the final reduced models to allow for a direct comparison between the predictor variables in the regression model and the criterion variable being studied. For the data analysis, we used a CI of 95%, considering all those values that had a *P* value of $<.05$ to be

statistically significant.

RESULTS

The asymptomatic group consisted of 40 participants, 28 of whom were women. The symptomatic group included 54 patients with TMD, 33 of whom were women. No statistically significant differences between the general characteristics of the two groups were found, except for educational level and medication ($P < .001$). The demographic characteristic data are summarised in Table 1. In addition, the mean of the results on V₃ of the trigeminal nerve between the participants with and without beards was evaluated in both groups. Statistically significant differences with a large effect size were found in asymptomatic subjects ($P < .001$; $d = 1.78$; $t = 3.80$) and also in patients with TMD ($P = .002$; $d = 1.14$; $t = 3.27$).

Reliability of 2-PD in asymptomatic individuals and in patients with temporomandibular disorder

Regarding the patients with TMD, intra-examiner reliability descriptive statistics, ICCs and associated 95% CIs, SEMs and MDC₉₀ values for trials 1, 2 and 3 for each rater are presented in Table 2. The ICC value for intra-rater reliability of single measures separated by 48 hours was .74 for V₁, .72 for V₂ and .70 for V₃. When the single measurements were separated by 9 days, the ICC value for intra-rater reliability was .79 for V₁, .70 for V₂ and .61 for V₃. With regard to total trials (trials 1, 2 and 3), the ICC value for

intra-rater reliability was .86 for V₁, .84 for V₂ and .72 for V₃.

Regarding the asymptomatic participants, intra-examiner reliability descriptive statistics, ICCs and associated 95% CIs, SEMs and MDC₉₀ values for trials 1 and 2 for each rater are also presented in Table 2. The intra-examiner reliability for V₁, V₂ and V₃ varied from .70 to .87. The greatest MDC₉₀ for these variables was 10.3 mm. In addition, a good-moderate reliability was obtained, with ICC values ranging from .79 to .83 for the test-retest reliability of examiner A and values ranging from .70 to .87 for examiner B. Interexaminer reliability descriptive statistics, ICCs and associated 95% CIs, SEMs and MDC₉₀ values for trials 1 and 2 for each rater are presented in Table 3. The ICC values of the interexaminer reliability for V₁, V₂ and V₃ were .64-.88; 11.2 mm was the highest value for the MDC₉₀ for the three variables.

Asymptomatic individuals vs patients with temporomandibular disorder

Independent *t* tests were used to compare the asymptomatic and symptomatic groups with respect to the V₁, V₂ and V₃ values, using the mean values from trials 1 and 2 (separated by 48 hours). The TMD group showed statistically significant differences in V₁, with a large effect size ($t = -5.39, P < .001, d = -1.25$), V₂, with a large effectsize ($t = -6.42, P < .001, d = -1.36$), and also for V₃ with a large effectsize ($t = -4.39, P < .001, d = -0.90$) compared with the asymptomatic group for the 2-PD test. The descriptive statistics' mean differences (95% CIs), and effect sizes between the two samples are presented in Table 4.

Correlation and multiple linear regression for patients with temporomandibular disorder

In the correlation analysis, positive moderate associations were found between the V₁, V₂ and V₃ 2-PD test values and the visual analog scale score ($r = .427$, $r = .505$, $P < .001$, and $r = .403$, $P < .05$, respectively). Regarding V₁ value, a moderate positive association was found with the CF-PDI ($r = .303$, $P < .05$), and a low positive association was found with the PCS ($r = .505$, $P < .001$). With regard to V₂ value, positive moderate associations were found with both CF-PDI and PCS variables ($r = .303$, and $r = .303$ respectively, $P < .05$). Finally, no associations were found between the V₃ value and both the CF-PDI and PCS scores ($P > .05$) (Table 5). In the first model, the criterion variable 2-PD test in V₁ was predicted by the pain intensity, thus explaining 16.7% of the variance. PCS ($\beta = .184$, $P = .161$) and CF-PDI ($\beta = .124$, $P = .393$) were not significant predictors. In the second model, the criterion variable 2-PD test in V₂ was predicted by the pain intensity and CF-PDI, thus explaining 30.1% of the variance. PCS ($\beta = .126$, $P = .316$) was not a significant predictor. Finally, in the third model, the criterion variable 2-PD test in V₃ was predicted by the pain intensity, thus explaining 14.6% of the variance. PCS ($\beta = -.201$, $P = .130$) and CF-PDI ($\beta = .009$, $P = .953$) were not significant predictors.

The main results obtained in the present study showed interexaminer (ICC .64-.88) and test-retest values (ICC .70-.87) for the asymptomatic participants. Given similar test-retest values were shown in the group of patients with TMD (ICC .72-.86), the reliability was considered good-

moderate. Statistically significant differences with a large effect size were obtained between the asymptomatic participants and the patients with TMD regarding the mean values from trials of the three trigeminal branch measurements.

Although there is not much information about the reliability of the 2-PD test measurement in the craniofacial region, there is information about other areas of the body. Catley et al¹² conducted a study in which a procedure similar to ours was performed on the neck, back, hand and foot; they obtained good test-retest reliability (.79-.86) and a good-moderate interexaminer reliability (.62-.81).

Regarding the comparison between the asymptomatic participants and the patients with TMD in the 2-PD test, the independent *t* tests showed that the patients with TMD had a significantly poorer tactile acuity than the asymptomatic participants. To decide whether a threshold value from an affected site indicates an abnormal sensory function, it can be compared with normal values from a healthy control population.¹⁹ Meyer and Bagheri³⁶ have found that in the forehead (V₁; trigeminal ophthalmic branch), an abnormal distance is considered >22 mm. In the maxillary zone (V₂; trigeminal maxillary branch), this is equivalent to 17 mm, and in the chin (V₃; trigeminal mandibular branch), a distance >18 mm is considered abnormal. The results of the present study found that the asymptomatic participants were within the normal ranges in the 2-PD test, with the exception of V₃; however, the area was not exactly the same. The patients with TMD showed distances greater than those described by Meyer and Bagheri³⁴ in all regions evaluated. Other studies with normative data have

also been published regarding 2-PD tests in the trigeminal region. For example, Nolan³⁵ had found that the normal values of the 2-PD test were 14.9 mm in an area innervated by the ophthalmic branch, 11.9 mm in an area innervated by the trigeminal maxillary branch and 10.4 mm for an area of the mandibular branch.

The group of patients with TMD showed greater distances than those reported as normal distances in the 2-PD test compared with the asymptomatic participants. It therefore appears that tactile acuity in the trigeminal region is impaired in patients with TMD. Several studies in the scientific literature have found that patients with various chronic pain conditions also have impaired tactile acuity, as measured through the 2-PD test. For example, Moseley³⁶ had found that tactile acuity was reduced in the area of usual pain in patients with chronic back pain. Luedtke et al³⁷ had also found reduced upper cervical tactile acuity in patients with migraine compared with headache-free controls. A systematic review and meta-analysis conducted by Catley et al³⁸ had found tactile acuity deficits in people with various chronic non-neuropathic pain conditions, such as arthritis, complex regional pain syndrome and chronic low back pain, but not in burning mouth syndrome. These findings are in accordance with those found in this study.

Regarding the physiopathological mechanisms underlying the presence of maintained pain that could explain many of the differences found between patients with TMD and asymptomatic subjects would be found in the first place, the processes of maladaptive and dysfunctional neuroplasticity caused by the presence of chronic pain in areas related to the

processing of sensitive information, such as the primary somatosensory cortex.³⁹ This cortical reorganisation has been reported in patients with chronic low back pain¹⁰ and complex regional syndrome.⁹ In addition to this, patients with persistent pain tend to show lower levels of physical activity due to disuse of the painful region, poorer sensorimotor control, lower levels of strength and influence of psychosocial variables such as erroneous beliefs, fear of movement or dysfunctional thoughts.⁴⁰⁻⁴² All these could also affect the processing of somatosensory information and could have contributed to the differences between patients with TMD and asymptomatic subjects.

Several studies suggest that tactile acuity can be trained and can improve with practice.^{43,44} Studies have found that repeated evaluation over time causes a training effect, and probably, this improvement in tactile acuity could influence reliability.¹² In patients population with reduced tactile acuity, only 30 minutes of tactile discrimination training was sufficient to induce a significant improvement in threshold after 2-PD, which was maintained for 48 hours.⁴³ However, Godde et al⁴⁵ have found that 2 hours of tactile training resulted in relevant improvements in discrimination between two points, but 30 minutes of training was insufficient. Therefore, it appears that the learning threshold for tactile acuity is somewhere between a repeated assessment of over 30 minutes and <2 hours of training¹² although further research would be needed to clarify this. In relation to the analysis of correlations, the main results showed moderate and positive associations between poorer tactile acuity in the three branches of the trigeminal nerve and greater pain intensity. This is an interesting finding

due to the current controversy in the current state of the art. Flor⁴⁶ and Wand et al⁴⁷ have argued that the magnitude of cortical reorganisation appears to be related to the intensity and duration of symptoms such as pain. However, a systematic review and meta-analysis conducted by Catley et al³⁸ has shown no significant associations between tactile acuity and pain intensity or duration of symptoms. Harvie et al⁸ have hypothesised that tactile dysfunction could relate to pain intensity and duration in patients with chronic neck pain; these findings would be in accordance with those found in this study of patients with TMD.

Finally, moderate-low and positive associations were found between poorer tactile acuity in the maxillary and ophthalmic branches of the trigeminal nerve and higher levels of disability and pain catastrophism. This association appears to indicate that higher levels of disability as well as poorer scores on psychosocial variables, together with the presence of persistent pain, could contribute to greater somatosensory aberrations. Little scientific evidence is available on these findings in patients with TMD; however, our hypothesis is that higher levels of disability and greater psychosocial influences could contribute to the deconditioning of the affected area (eg lower levels of physical activity, lower strength, poorer motor control), which could secondarily lead to abnormal results in somatosensory variables such as tactile acuity. Regarding our hypothesis, Wand et al⁴⁷ have shown that patients with chronic low back pain have impaired motor and sensitivity function, and it has been proposed that those motor and sensitivity alterations might be a manifestation of a disturbance in body perception related to cortical changes in patients

with chronic low back pain.⁴⁸ In addition, another variable of high importance could be the self-efficacy beliefs. A several number of studies have found a close relationship between high levels of disability and low self-efficacy.^{49,50} La Touche et al⁵¹ and Duray et al⁵⁰ found that the presence of higher levels of self-efficacy in patients with CLBP determined better active coping strategies, motivating patients towards better physical condition in terms of higher physical activity levels, higher functional reach, greater active range of motion and a lower presence of somatosensory disorders. This may be interesting to consider as they support our hypothesis above. However, this must be taken with caution because these studies were about chronic low back pain and not about patients with TMD. It would have been interesting to include the evaluation of the self-efficacy variable in order to give greater support to the hypothesis proposed by the authors. This could be considered as a limitation.

Clinical implications

The main finding of this study is that the reliability of the 2-PD test can be considered good-moderate. Therefore, the 2-PD test should be considered clinically when assessing tactile acuity of the trigeminal region, both in asymptomatic individuals and in patients with TMD. In addition to this, it is important to emphasise that the MDC was also explored in this study. This could be considered of clinical interest for reassessments during patients' management.

In addition, some data suggest that tactile discrimination training could

have a positive influence on the pain and symptoms of patients with chronic pain.^{52,53} Although further research is needed into this type of training, the results of this study suggest that tactile acuity measurement in patients with TMD should be taken into account clinically, both for the assessment of somatosensory deficits and for developing future rehabilitation protocols.

Limitations

This study presents several limitations that should be considered when interpreting the results. First, it is not possible to establish a cause-effect relationship between the results obtained between tactile acuity and patients with TMD. Second, previous studies have shown differences in discriminatory sensitivity between men and women; therefore, it would be interesting in future studies to evaluate the differences between both sexes. Third, and in order to prevent a cutaneous sensitisation process, intra-examiner measurements were conducted 48 hours apart, which should be considered in the interpretation of the results. Finally, It would have been interesting to assess self-efficacy beliefs in order to establish a relationship with the other variables of the present research.

CONCLUSIONS

The reliability of the 2-PD test in the trigeminal area can be considered good-moderate. The results of the 2-PD test for patients with TMD showed greater distances than in asymptomatic individuals, suggesting that tactile acuity in

the trigeminal region is impaired in patients with TMD. Tactile acuity using the 2-PD test in patients with TMD should be taken into account clinically in the somatosensorial assessment of these patients.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

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TABLE 1 Demographic characteristics of the asymptomatic participants and the patients with TMD

Measures	Asymptomatic (n = 40)	TMD (n = 54)	P value
Age	37.62 ± 13.56	42.31 ± 12.11	.08
Height (cm)	166.57 ± 10.53	165.22 ± 8.42	.49
Weight (kg)	65.20 ± 12.49	66.89 ± 11.91	.50
Sex			
Male	12 (30.0)	21 (38.9)	.39
Female	28 (70.0)	33 (61.1)	
Educational level			
Primary education	0 (0.0)	5 (9.3)	<.001**
Secondary education	3 (7.5)	22 (40.7)	
College education	37 (92.5)	27 (50.0)	
Marital status			
Single	24 (60.0)	26 (48.1)	.59
Married	10 (25.0)	19 (35.2)	
Divorced	5 (12.5)	6 (11.1)	
Widowed	1 (2.5)	4 (5.6)	
Dominant side			
Right	38 (95.0)	45 (83.3)	.11
Left	2 (5)	9 (16.7)	
Medication			
No medication	34 (85.0)	18 (33.3)	<.001**
NSAIDs and analgesics	6 (15.0)	27 (50.0)	
Low-intensity opioids	0 (0.0)	7 (13.0)	
TCA	0 (0.0)	2 (3.7)	

Values are mean ± SD and n (%).

Abbreviations: NSAIDs, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs; TCAs, tricyclic antidepressants; TMD, temporomandibular disorders. ** $P < .001$

TABLE 2 Intra-examiner reliability in the asymptomatic participants and in the patients with TMD

Group	Measures	48 h between trials (trial 1-trial 2)							9 d between trials (trial 2-trial 3)			
		Trial 1 ($\bar{X} \pm SD$)	Trial 2 ($\bar{X} \pm SD$)	Trial 3 ($\bar{X} \pm SD$)	ICC	95% CI ICC	SEM	MDC ₉₀	ICC	95% CI ICC	SEM	MDC ₉₀
TMD	V ₁ (mm)	27.1 ± 9.2	26.1 ± 9.1	23.7 ± 8.8	.74	.56-.85	5.8	13.7	.79	.63-.87	5.3	12.3
	V ₂ (mm)	26.1 ± 8.7	23.3 ± 8.2	22.2 ± 8.9	.72	.52-.84	5.6	13.1	.70	.48-.82	5.8	12.2
	V ₃ (mm)	28.6 ± 7.1	28.4 ± 7.9	26.2 ± 6.2	.70	.48-.82	4.7	11.1	.61	.32-.77	4.8	11.1
AG	V ₁ (mm)	A 19.0 ± 4.7	A 19.2 ± 4.8	–	.81	.65-.90	2.6	6.2	–	–	–	–
		B 19.1 ± 4.7	B 18.7 ± 4.8	–	.80	.63-.90	2.7	6.3	–	–	–	–
	V ₂ (mm)	A 16.5 ± 3.6	A 16.8 ± 4.2	–	.83	.68-.91	2.1	5.0	–	–	–	–
		B 16.5 ± 4.1	B 15.6 ± 4.1	–	.87	.76-.93	1.9	4.5	–	–	–	–
	V ₃ (mm)	A 22.7 ± 6.3	A 23.1 ± 6.7	–	.79	.65-.90	3.7	8.8	–	–	–	–
		B 23.3 ± 6.9	B 22.2 ± 6.1	–	.70	.63-.90	4.4	10.3	–	–	–	–

Abbreviations: CI, confidence interval; Ex, examiner; ICC, intra-class correlation coefficient; MDC₉₀, minimal detectable change at the 90% confidence level; mm, millimetres; SEM, standard error of measurement; TMD, temporomandibular disorders; V₁, trigeminal ophthalmic branch; V₂, trigeminal maxillary branch; V₃, trigeminal mandibular branch; $\bar{X} \pm SD$, mean standard deviation.

TABLE 3 Interexaminer reliability in the asymptomatic participants

Measures	Trial 1						Trial 2					
	Ex A ($\bar{X} \pm SD$)	Ex B ($\bar{X} \pm SD$)	ICC	95% CI ICC	SEM	MDC ₉₀	Ex A ($\bar{X} \pm SD$)	Ex B ($\bar{X} \pm SD$)	ICC	95% CI ICC	SEM	MDC ₉₀
V1 (mm)	18.9 ± 4.7	19.1 ± 4.7	.71	.45-.83	3.1	7.4	19.2 ± 4.8	18.7 ± 4.7	.70	.43-.84	3.2	7.6
V2 (mm)	16.5 ± 3.6	16.5 ± 4.1	.80	.63-.90	2.2	5.2	16.8 ± 4.2	15.6 ± 4.1	.86	.73-.92	1.9	4.5
V3 (mm)	22.7 ± 6.3	23.3 ± 6.9	.64	.32-.80	4.8	11.2	23.1 ± 6.7	22.2 ± 6.1	.88	.77-.93	2.9	6.8

Abbreviations: CI, confidence interval; Ex, examiner; ICC, intra-class correlation coefficient; MDC₉₀, minimal detectable change at the 90% confidence level; mm, millimetres; SEM, standard error of measurement; V₁, trigeminal ophthalmic branch; V₂, trigeminal maxillary branch; V₃, trigeminal mandibular branch; $\bar{X} \pm SD$, mean standard deviation.

TABLE 4 Comparison between the asymptomatic participants and the patients with TMD for the 2-point discrimination test.

Measures	Asymptomatic participants ($\bar{X} \pm SD$)	Patients with TMD ($\bar{X} \pm SD$)	Mean differences (95% CI)	Cohen's <i>d</i> (effect size)
V ₁	19.0 ± 4.0	26.6 ± 7.6	-7.6 (-10.5 to -4.7)**	<i>d</i> = -1.25
V ₂	16.4 ± 3.6	24.4 ± 7.5	-8.0 (-10.6 to -5.5)**	<i>d</i> = -1.36
V ₃	22.5 ± 4.5	27.1 ± 5.6	-4.6 (-6.7 to -2.5)**	<i>d</i> = -0.90

Abbreviations: CI, confidence interval; TMD, temporomandibular disorders; V₁, trigeminal ophthalmic branch; V₂, trigeminal maxillary branch; V₃, trigeminal mandibular branch; $\bar{X} \pm SD$, mean standard deviation. ***P* < .001

TABLE 5 Pearson's correlation analysis in the patients with temporomandibular disorders

Measures	VAS	CF-PDI	PCS
V ₁	0.427**	0.303*	0.287*
V ₂	0.504**	0.482**	0.319*
V ₃	0.403*	0.203	-0.075

Abbreviations: CF-PDI, craniofacial pain and disability inventory; PCS, pain catastrophising scale; V₁, trigeminal ophthalmic branch; V₂, trigeminal maxillary branch; V₃, trigeminal mandibular branch; VAS, visual analog scale. **P* < .05; ***P* < .001.

FIGURES

Figure 1. Flowchart of the study

Figure 2. Representation of the assessed points in the two- point discrimination test: the three branches of the trigeminal nerve.